

The Timbre in Popular Song (TiPS) Corpus

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Introduction

Our project analyzes the understudied parameters of timbre and texture and their interactions with musical form in a new popular-music corpus, Timbre in Popular Song (TiPS). This study addresses two problems in popular-music scholarship: lack of research on timbre and texture, and underrepresentation of non-male and non-white artists in both popular music and its scholarship. We have developed and refined a comprehensive system for annotating timbre and texture in popular music, as well as a novel sampling method, the Anti-Discriminatory Alignment System (ADAS), that identifies and addresses imbalances in representation of artists' gender, race, and ethnicity.

Timbre (tone color) and texture (musical layers) are important stylistic and structural parameters that are highly perceptually salient. In popular music, timbre is an important marker: listeners can identify genres and often specific artists in under a second based on timbre (Gjerdingen and Perrott 2008, Mace et al. 2012], with no time to perceive other musical features that unfold gradually. Popular music is well known for the wide timbral variety afforded by both electronic and acoustic instruments, as well as the performance tradition of using gritty-sounding timbres for expressive effect—e.g., distorted electric guitar, the raspy or growly quality of vocal fry, or the “dirty,” gravelly saxophone sound created by humming. Formal sections in popular music are usually more clearly defined than in classical music and are often marked by contrasts in timbre and texture. Yet despite the importance of these parameters in musical expression and structure, and their centrality to music listening, their functional roles in this repertoire have not been closely examined or theorized.

Another problem in popular-music research addressed by our study is the inequitable representation of artists. The comparative neglect of music by women, people of colour, and other marginalized groups, which has contributed to music theory's endemic sexism (Hisama 2019, Maus 1993, McClary 1991) and deeply ingrained white racial frame (Ewell 2020 and 2023, Gopinath 2009, Kang 2009), has only recently begun to be addressed by scholars. In this project, we seek to counter biases against non-white and non-male artists by addressing their underrepresentation in research on popular music. Extant popular-music corpora such as the Rolling Stone corpus (De Clercq and Temperley 2011, Temperley and De Clercq 2013, 2017) and McGill Billboard corpus (Burgoyne 2011, White and Quinn 2018, White et al. 2022), the two popular-music corpora that have been most used by music analysts, are heavily biased toward white male artists. Our new corpus has more equitable representation: our novel sampling method for song selection (Shea et al. 2024) balances genre typicality with gender and racial

diversity as well as chronological representation. This helps counter the marginalization of women artists and artists of colour in many popular-music genres and studies. Our new framework for anti-discriminatory sampling in music corpus studies modifies the methodologies of our discipline to help disrupt real-world biases.

The initial iteration of the TiPS corpus consists of 400 songs from the 1990s, comprising 100 songs each from four disparate genres with contrasting musical styles: country, pop, heavy metal, and hip hop. Since our focus is to make comparisons across genres, we limited this initial stage to songs from a single decade. We plan to expand the corpus, adding 3200 more songs from six decades and three more important genres--rhythm & blues/soul, rock, and electronic dance music, for a total of 3600 songs released between 1960 and 2019, encompassing many of the main genres of popular music. A planned third phase of the project will add the genres of punk, funk, and ska/reggae.

Song selection in TiPS balances genre typicality and chronological representation with considerations of diverse identities: our approach to song selection considers artists' gender, race, and ethnicity, to help counter the systemic biases often propagated in music corpora and better reflect real-world diversity. Details related to timbre, texture, and form for each song are encoded and will be analyzed by genre to identify normative timbral and textural combinations, as well as typical differences among genres. Previous popular music corpora have been encoded primarily with respect to form and pitch (e.g., Burgoyne et al. 2011, De Clercq & Temperley 2011); our TiPS database is the first multi-genre corpus to be constructed for encoding timbral and textural information (the hip-hop corpus in Duinker & Martin 2017 includes annotations for texture and, to some degree, timbre).

Corpus Construction

Our Anti-Discriminatory Alignment System or ADAS derives a smaller “child” corpus from a larger “parent” one by applying a sampling method that is intentionally designed to counterbalance discriminatory forces. The child corpus includes more diverse artist identities and also may better represent the musical diversity within a style or genre (See Example 1). For each of the four genres in the current TiPS corpus (pop, hip hop, metal, and country), we compiled a parent corpus of 150–225 songs based on pre-existing sources such as Billboard charts, and encoded demographic variables of gender, race, and ethnicity for each artist. This information was used to create a child corpus for each genre. The child corpora each consist of 100 songs, balanced for artist representation (limited to 5 songs per artist or group) and even chronological distribution across the decade (10 songs per year, 1990–1999).

Example 1: A schematization of the Anti-Discriminatory Alignment System.

Parent corpora for each genre were derived from various sources, as no single source provides parallel lists across genres. The parent corpus for pop music was drawn from Billboard’s “Top Songs of the 90s” list, which includes 500 songs in a variety of genres. Song titles were filtered through iTunes to identify genre; 182 songs that iTunes labelled as “pop” constitute the pop parent corpus. The hip-hop parent corpus includes songs that were ranked #1 on Billboard’s “Hot Rap Songs” chart between 1990 and 1999, totalling 163 songs. The country parent corpus consists of the top 20 “Hot Country Songs” from the Billboard Year-End charts from 1990 to 1999, totalling 200 songs. Unlike the other three genres, there are no Billboard charts for heavy metal, so we derived the metal parent corpus of 225 songs from four lists based on critical acclaim: Hartmann 2018, Loudwire Staff 2020, Pasbani 2017, and Podoshen 2017. As these lists included songs that might be classified as hard rock or alternative rock, we developed a genre-filtering method like that used for the pop parent corpus, but with additional input from expert metal listeners.

Our demographic encoding system, developed from work by Shea (Shea 2022, Shea et al. 2024), records whether the lead artist or any band members belong to a marginalized racial, ethnic, or gender group, when explicit in print or online resources. We adopted the racial and ethnic categories used by The Music Coalition of the Annenberg Inclusion Initiative at the University of Southern California, which classifies these identities as underrepresented in the music industry: Black/African American, Hispanic/Latino, Asian, Native American/Alaska Native, Native Hawaiian/Pacific Islander, Middle Eastern, and Other/Mixed Race (Smith et al. 2018). With respect to gender, we considered any gender identity other than male as subject to marginalization. We also recorded a variable called “primary” that reflects the agency of marginalized artists within their ensembles. This variable is encoded as positive if either the title/lead member of the ensemble or more than half of the group’s members identify as racial, ethnic, or gender minorities. Student research assistants were trained in a 90-minute session to learn and practice the demographic encoding method described above, contextualized by critical discussion about issues of equity, diversity, and inclusion and the limitations of our approach. Following this training, they encoded demographic variables of gender, race, and ethnicity for each artist across the four parent corpora. For each entry, demographic encoders included their sources of information and commented on their decision-making processes as needed. Demographic information was cross-checked by team members in two ways: verifying a random sample of 35% of the encoded data for each genre/decade unit and reviewing each entry to ensure coherence between the details in the comments and the data.

Our study aims to make our corpus more representative of the overall population of the United States during the chronological window represented by the corpus. We also opted to make this a relative rather than absolute goal: the minimum acceptable proportion for representation in each genre's child corpus was reckoned based on the diversity within its parent corpus, with more initial diversity resulting in higher targets than corpora with less initial diversity. We therefore set target proportions for gender and for race/ethnicity by calculating the geometric mean—an averaging function designed for proportions—between the proportion in the parent corpus and the relevant US Census data for that time period.

Based on our demographic encoding, we calculated the proportions of marginalized artists in each parent corpus by gender and race/ethnicity. We then set target proportions for gender and race/ethnicity for the child corpora, to make them more representative of the overall population of the United States during the chronological window represented by the corpora. We also opted to make this a relative rather than absolute goal: the minimum acceptable proportion for representation in each genre's child corpus was based on the diversity within its parent corpus, with more initial diversity resulting in higher targets than corpora with less initial diversity. We therefore set target proportions for gender and for race/ethnicity by calculating the geometric mean—an averaging function designed for proportions—between the proportion in the parent corpus and the relevant US Census data for that decade. In constructing the child corpora, we retained all songs by marginalized artists from the parent corpora. Next, in cases where the target proportion was below the population proportion, we supplemented the corpus via other sources to increase representation. Such adjustments for gender were made to the country, hip hop, and metal corpora, and adjustments for race/ethnicity were made to the country corpus. Example 2 shows differences in gender representation by the proportion between parent and child corpora for each genre; it also shows the same comparison for racial/ethnic representation. We recognize that there are multiple parameters of diversity, and any sampling method is necessarily imperfect. Our approach is not a solution to deeply ingrained issues of inequity, but our anti-discriminatory sampling framework represents a step toward more inclusive music scholarship.

Example 2: Proportions of marginalized artists in parent and child corpora compared to proportions in the U.S. population for 1990-1999 based on census data (horizontal line).

Song Annotation

Our theoretical approach to encoding form, texture, and timbre in popular songs is based on recent corpus-study methods in music scholarship that demonstrate large-scale patterns across time, genre, and culture, allowing for data analysis providing insight into these trends. Our categories of formal section types are based on De Clercq 2012, Summach 2012, and Temperley 2018, which are substantially in agreement: core song sections are verses, choruses, and bridges; ancillary song sections are intros, prechoruses, postchoruses, solos/instrumentals, outros, and links. Our analysis of texture is based on Allan F. Moore’s model of rock texture as comprising melody, harmonic filler, bass, and explicit beat layers (Moore 2012), with the addition of Megan Lavengood’s novelty layer (2017, 2020). Our encoding of timbre is entirely new, influenced by research in Reymore 2020, Zeller 2020, and White 2021.

Encoded metadata for each song includes the artist(s), song and album title, Billboard rank, release year, and a link to the source recording used. Information about timbre and texture is encoded by formal section; each row in the dataset corresponds to one formal section of a song, with variables listed in columns. Repeating sections (e.g., verse, chorus) are numbered in the order they occur—e.g., the first and second choruses are labelled “C1” and “C2,” respectively. Variables related to timbre and texture were recorded for each formal section, as shown in Example 3.

Category	Name	Definition	Format
Form	Formal Unit	Formal module type	Categorical-S
	Timestamp	Time at beginning of formal unit	Time (min:sec)
	Timbral Marker	Whether a salient timbral event begins unit	Binary
	Change in Timbral Profile	Whether there is a salient change in overall timbre from previous unit	Binary
Instrumentation	Explicit Beat Layer	Instruments articulating pattern of beats	Categorical-M
	Functional Bass Layer	Instruments playing lowest pitched layer	Categorical-M
	Harmonic Fill Layer	Instruments filling the registral space between bass and melody	Categorical-M
	Melodic Layer	Instruments carrying a melody	Categorical-M
	Novelty Layer	Instruments that provide coloristic effects	Categorical-M
Texture	Texture Category	Describes general texture type	Categorical-S
	Variation	Describes how timbre and/or texture changes within a formal unit	Categorical-S
	Texture Rating	General textural density	Integer
Voice	Number of Voices	Number of distinct voices singing melodically	Integer
	Vocal Production	Most prominent vocal qualities of the lead vocalist(s)	Categorical-M
	Speak/Sing	Mode of delivery by lead vocalist(s)	Categorical-M
	Backup Vocals	Textural function of the background vocals	Categorical-M

S = single variable selection; M = multiple possible selections

Example 3: Timbre and texture variables encoded in the TiPS corpus.

These variables were created and refined collaboratively by the authors. After compiling an initial set of proposed variables, several authors applied them to sample songs. We discussed the results, revising variables and definitions in response. We then completed a second round of encoding using the refined variables and a second round of collaborative revision. Next, research assistants (RAs) were trained to encode variables and practice song annotation in a 2-hour workshop. Each RA completed five songs, which were carefully reviewed by one of the authors; validation assignments were distributed so that each student received detailed feedback from five different team members, and revised their annotations as needed. We established a Slack workspace for the project, which allows research assistants and team members to be in communication with each other while working. This resulted in a third stage of collaborative refinements to the variables and definitions, after which the RAs continued encoding. Encoding for a sample song is shown in Example 4 below, and encoded data for the entire pop corpus is available in the Appendix.

formal unit timestamp	timb. marker	timb. change	explicit beat	funct. bass	harm. filler	melody	novelty	texture cat.	variation texture rating # of voices	vocal prod.	delivery	backup voc.	comments
1 0:01	0	Increase		drums e bass:clean e gtr:clean, synth:dark, synth:strings			sample:wind chime, lead voc, sec voc	varied	1	0		other	Spoken & processed voc
C1 0:34	1	same		drums e bass:clean e gtr:clean, synth:strings, synth:dark		lead voc, sec voc		no mel	1	3	0	other	Secondary vocal spoken
C2 0:52	1	same		drums e bass:clean e gtr:clean, synth:strings, synth:dark, bg voc		lead voc	lead voc, sec voc, pno	mel/accomp	1	4	M airy/breathy	sung harmony, other	timbral marker: piano
V1 1:13	1	same		drums e bass:clean e gtr:clean, synth:strings, synth:dark		lead voc		mel/accomp	1	2	1 airy/breathy	sung	
P1 1:33	1	same		drums e bass:clean e gtr:clean, pno, synth:dark, synth:strings, vibes		lead voc		mel/accomp	1	3	1 airy/breathy	sung	
C2 1:41	1	same		drums e bass:clean e gtr:clean, pno, synth:dark, synth:strings, bg voc		lead voc	sample:wind chime, lead voc, sec voc	mel/accomp	1	4	M airy/breathy	sung harmony, other	pno unison w/synth
V2 2:02	1	same		drums e bass:clean e gtr:clean, synth:bright, synth:dark		lead voc	sample:wind chime	mel/accomp	1	3	1 airy/breathy,creaky/fry	sung	Synth high counter mel
V3 2:21	1	same		drums e bass:clean e gtr:clean, synth:bright, synth:dark, vibes		lead voc	secondary vocal	mel/accomp	1	3	1 airy/breathy,creaky/fry	sung other	Spoken & processed voc
P2 2:42	1	same		drums e bass:clean e gtr:clean, pno, synth:dark, synth:strings, vibes		lead voc		mel/accomp	1	3	1 airy/breathy,belt/chest	sung	
C3 2:50	1	same		drums e bass:clean e gtr:clean; pno, synth:dark, synth:strings, vibes, bg voc		lead voc	sample:wind chime, sec voc	mel/accomp	1	5	M airy/breathy,falsetto/head	sung harm, counter mel, other	Deeper hit on downbeat
C4 3:21	1	same		drums e bass:clean e gtr:clean; pno, synth:dark, synth:strings, vibes, bg voc		lead voc	secondary vocal	mel/accomp	1	4	M airy/breathy	most melody,other	
C5 3:40	0	decrease		drums e bass:clean e gtr: clean, synth:bright, synth:strings, vibes		lead voc	sample:wind chime, sec voc	varied	1	3	1 airy/breathy	sung other	Progressive drop-out
C6 3:59	1	decrease		drums e bass:clean e gtr:clean; pno, synth:dark, synth:strings, vibes, bg voc		lead voc	sample:wind chime, sec voc	varied	1	4	M airy/breathy	sung harmony,other	Progressive drop-out

Example 4: Sample annotation for Janet Jackson, “That’s the Way Love Goes” (1993).

After annotations for each genre/decade unit are completed, all will be cross-checked by other encoders. Analytical disagreements will be resolved by team members with expertise in that genre. Team members will cross-validate 35% of the annotated corpus and measure inter-analyst agreement with a kappa statistic to strengthen the analyses. Thus, all songs will be analyzed by at least two research assistants, and many will be additionally verified by a team member.

Project Status

Song encoding of the 400-song TiPS corpus is complete, and we are currently cross-checking the annotations. Team members will measure inter-analyst agreement with a kappa statistic to strengthen the analyses, and analytical disagreements will be resolved by team members with expertise in that genre. The pop corpus is presently available as a CSV file (see below), and the country, metal, and hip-hop corpora will be finished soon, all eventually becoming open-access datasets. This allows our team and future researchers to do statistical analysis using a variety of programs and programming languages, such as Excel, R, or Python.

Our first analytical goal is to define normative timbral, textural, and formal characteristics of each genre and identify the principal similarities and differences in such norms among genres. For example, we will identify which timbral vocal qualities (e.g., vocal fry, breathiness, growling, belting) are typical of each genre, and how the function of background vocals varies across genres. We will examine how timbral and textural characteristics vary with formal

function, and how they interact with genre. Statistical analysis of our annotations can answer questions such as: which instruments are most commonly used in a given formal section type, and how does this vary from genre to genre? We will also address relationships among the 14 annotated variables, such as the relationships between instrumentation and texture. Our second analytical goal is to identify changes in timbral and textural norms over time, both within and across genres. For example, do certain instruments or instrument combinations become more or less common in different genres over time? How do trends in timbre and texture over time map across genres, and can we observe cross-fertilization of timbral and textural techniques across genres? Such changes may relate to cultural or technological shifts and may help us to better understand how such factors interact with trends in popular music. From these analyses, we will develop new theoretical models for timbre and texture in popular music and will adapt and disseminate our findings both as scholarly output (presentations, publications) and pedagogical resources (e.g., syllabi, lesson plans).

Conclusion

Our study offers a model for creating a more equitable corpus of popular songs using a new demographically adjusted sampling method, as well as a new encoding system for timbre and texture, which are treated as structural parameters for the first time in a corpus of popular songs. The next phase of our project will expand the repertoire beyond our initial four genres of pop, country, metal, and hip hop to add three more important genres: rhythm & blues, rock, and electronic dance music. We will also expand the corpus beyond the 1990s to encompass all decades in the sixty-year span between the 1960s and 2010s. For a more concise version of this information see Reymore et al. 2022, and for a more detailed discussion see Shea et al. 2024 (both linked in the appendix).

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